

**ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF COGNITIVE-BEHAVIORAL THERAPY
IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DEPRESSION: A
LITERATURE REVIEW**

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Depression is a mood disorder resulting from cognitive and functional changes, making it one of the main disabling illnesses. Given this, cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) emerged, based on phenomenological concepts, as an effective therapy in its treatment, providing favorable clinical outcomes, from symptom remission to relapse prevention. This shows the relevance of CBT in this context, whether as a single therapy or as a combined

therapy. **OBJECTIVE:** To carry out a literature search regarding the value and relevance of using cognitive behavioral therapy in the treatment of patients with depression. **METHODOLOGY:** A bibliographical research was carried out on the topic, in the Scielo, Revista Brasileira de Psiquiatria and Revista Brasileira de terapias cognitive databases, using the keywords “Depression”, “Therapy” and “Cognitive Behavioral”, about therapy as a treatment for patients with depressive disorders. **RESULTS:** CBT proved to be effective in treating depression, both in primary cases and in relapse situations, acting to reduce the clinical symptoms of depressive disorder (DD). Furthermore, it presented a high level of evidence when compared to other therapies, such as medication. Therefore, it is possible to consider it as one of the main and first-choice treatments for TD, covering the different aspects of the disease with better prognoses. Cognitive-behavioral therapy is the best-researched form of treatment involving any psychological disorder, and is even considered to be equally or better effective than pharmacotherapy for depression, as it provides a longer-lasting response and is more resistant to recurrences. Cognitive therapy aims to act in three phases: focus on automatic thoughts and depressogenic schemes; focus on the person's style of relating to others; changing behaviors in order to better cope with the problem situation. In this way, with the active participation of the patient, the professional ensures that the individual undergoing treatment is able to identify, recognize and generate alternative and accurate thoughts about situations.

Keywords : Depression. Psychotherapy. Cognitive behavioral therapy.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Therefore, the use of cognitive behavioral therapy to treat depression provides beneficial results. It helps guide patients in understanding what affects them emotionally and, mainly, in dealing with the adversities involved.

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